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New species and new records of leaf beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) from Northern Thailand

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Abstract. Six new species of leaf beetles are described from Thailand: *Plagiosterna suwattanae* sp. n., *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n., *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n., *Sinoluperoides chenichirae* sp. n. The figures of general view and genitalia are given for them and some of related species. The aedeagi for two species previously known only from females, *Basilepta subtuberosa* Tan, 1988 and *Bathseba tristis* (Medvedev, 2001), are imaged for the first time. Some diagnostic characters of *Bathseba tristis* and *Pagria vietnamica* Moseyko et Medvedev, 2005 have been clarified. The first identification keys to all known species of the genus *Luperocella* Jacoby, 1900 is proposed. *Platycorynus dilaticollis* (Jacoby, 1892), sp. resurr. is resurrected from synonyms of *P. chalybeus* Marshall, 1864, and *Luperocella hirsuta* Jacoby, 1900, sp. resurr. is resurrected from synonyms of *L. albopilosa* (Jacoby, 1892). The following 17 species are recorded for the first time from Thailand: *Lema mediolineata* Jacoby, 1908, *Lema semiregularis* Jacoby, 1908, *Iphimoides pallidulus* (Jacoby, 1889), *Parascela hirsuta* (Jacoby, 1908), *Platycorynus dilaticollis* (Jacoby, 1892), *Basilepta subtuberosa* Tan, 1988, *Aplosonyx ornatus* (Jacoby, 1892), *Gallerucida moseri* Weise, 1922, *Hoplosaenidea aerosa* (Laboissière, 1933), *Kanarella unicolor* Jacoby, 1896, *Vietoluperus alleculoides* Medvedev et Dang, 1981, *Hyphasis limbatipennis* Jacoby, 1889, *Laboissierea minuta* Medvedev, 2009, *Podontia lutea* (Olivier, 1790), *Xuthea orientalis* Baly, 1865, *Prionispa cheni* Staines, 2007, *Prionispa opacipennis* Chen et Yu, 1962. *Bathseba tristis* is recorded for the first time from Vietnam.

Key words: Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Eumolpinae, Galerucinae, Cassidinae, Thailand, Vietnam, new species.

Новые виды и новые указания жуков-листоедов (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) из Северного Таиланда

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Резюме. Описано шесть новых видов жуков-листоедов из Таиланда: *Plagiosterna suwattanae* sp. n., *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n., *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n., *Sinoluperoides chenichirae* sp. n. Для них и некоторых родственных видов приведены фотографии габитуса и полового аппарата. Впервые даны иллюстрации аedeгусов для известных ранее только по самкам *Basilepta subtuberosa* Tan, 1988 и *Bathseba tristis* (Медведев, 2001). Уточнены некоторые диагностические признаки *Bathseba tristis* и *Pagria vietnamica* Moseyko et Medvedev, 2005. Дана первая определительная таблица для всех известных видов рода *Luperocella* Jacoby, 1900. *Platycorynus dilaticollis* (Jacoby, 1892), sp. resurr. восстановлен из синонимов *P. chalybeus* Marshall, 1864, а *Luperocella hirsuta* Jacoby, 1900, sp. resurr. – из синонимов *L. albopilosa* (Jacoby, 1892). Впервые для Таиланда указано 17 видов листоедов: *Lema mediolineata* Jacoby, 1908, *Lema semiregularis* Jacoby, 1908, *Iphimoides pallidulus* (Jacoby, 1889), *Parascela hirsuta* (Jacoby, 1908), *Platycorynus dilaticollis* (Jacoby, 1892), *Basilepta subtuberosa* Tan, 1988, *Aplosonyx ornatus* (Jacoby, 1892), *Gallerucida moseri* Weise, 1922, *Hoplosaenidea aerosa* (Laboissière, 1933), *Kanarella unicolor* Jacoby, 1896, *Vietoluperus alleculoides* Medvedev et Dang, 1981, *Hyphasis limbatipennis* Jacoby, 1889, *Laboissierea minuta* Medvedev, 2009, *Podontia lutea* (Olivier, 1790), *Xuthea orientalis* Baly, 1865, *Prionispa cheni* Staines, 2007, *Prionispa opacipennis* Chen et Yu, 1962. *Bathseba tristis* впервые приведен для фауны Вьетнама.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Eumolpinae, Galerucinae, Cassidinae, Таиланд, Вьетнам, новые виды.

The present paper is based on the examination of the material collected by the author in Northern Thailand in 2024 (near Thep Sadet village, Doi Saket District of Chiang Mai Province). This is a mountainous area located on the Khun Tan Range. In addition, material from the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (ZIN, St Petersburg, Russia), from the private collection of J. Bezděk (Brno, Czech Republic) as well as from the author's collection (PR, St Petersburg, Russia) were studied.

All measurements were made using an ocular grid mounted on MBS-20 stereomicroscope. Measurements of all segments were taken at their widest part, unless otherwise specifically stated. All the proportions of antennomeres and tarsomeres are given in standard units

(1 conventional unit = 0.025 mm). Measurements are given only for visible tarsomeres, that is, for ones I–III and V. All photos presented in this article were taken by the author with the exception of photos of *Pyrrhalta kwangtungensis* Gressitt and Kimoto, 1963 taken by J. Bezděk. Author's photographs of habitus were taken using a Canon EOS 80D digital camera with a combined Canon EF 70–200 mm f/4.0L IS USM and inverted following lenses: Olympus OM-System Zuiko Auto-T 100 mm f/2.8 for large species; Minolta MC Rokkor-PF 50 mm f/1.7 or Canon EF-S 60 mm f/2.8 Macro USM for medium size species and Olympus Zuiko Digital 35 mm f/3.5 Macro for *Pagria*. Photographs of aedeagi and spermathecae were taken using a Canon EOS 80D digital camera and a combined Canon EF

70–20 mm f/4.0L IS USM and inverted Canon EF-S 24 mm F2.8 STM lenses (to photograph spermathecae Canon Extender EF 1.4 X II was additionally used). Images at different focal planes were combined using Zerene Stacker Professional 1.04 software.

The present study has resulted in description of six new for science leaf beetle species, and 17 leaf beetle species are recorded for Thailand for the first time. The morphological characters and geographical distribution of some species are clarified, and provisional identification key is proposed for representatives of the genus *Luperocella* Jacoby, 1900.

Subfamily Criocerinae Latreille, 1804

Lema (Lema) mediolineata Jacoby, 1908

(Fig. 1)

Material. 3♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1100m N 18°56'48.3", E 99°21'22.4" 10.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but “11.V.2024”; 3♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 16.V.2024”; 2♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024”.

Notes. Oriental species of *Lema* Fabricius, 1798 were reviewed and keyed by Warchałowski [2011]. *Lema mediolineata* was known only from Myanmar (Burma Ruby Mines).

Distribution. Myanmar [Jacoby, 1908; Warchałowski, 2011], Northern Thailand (new record).

Lema (Lema) semiregularis Jacoby, 1908

(Fig. 2)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1040-1019m, N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" N 18°57'26", E 99°20'16 22.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”.

Notes. According to the description of the species given by Jacoby [1908] this species differs from other fulvous species with blue elytra in antennomere III shorter than antennomere IV and in coarse puncturation at the base of the elytra, which looks somewhat confused on account of the transversely rugose interstices.

I have never examined Indian representatives of this species but my specimen fully complies with all the diagnostic characters of *L. semiregularis* given above.

Distribution. India (Manipur, Malabar coast) [Jacoby, 1908; Warchałowski, 2011], Northern Thailand (new record).

Subfamily Eumolpinae Hope, 1841

Basilepta subtuberosa Tan, 1988

(Figs 3, 4, 27, 28)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1045-1015m N 18°57'8.5", E 99°20'42" - N 18°57'22", E 99°20'24" 20.V.2024”; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 25.V.2024”; 3♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1226-1400m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" - N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 27.V.2024”.

Notes. This species was described from Southern China (Yunnan) on base of two females (holotype and paratype). The specimens listed above almost completely correspond to all the characters of this species and its

image given by Tan with co-authors [Tan, 1988; Tan et al., 2005]. In addition, thanks to the kindness of A. Moseyko I was able to compare my specimens with the photographs of type specimens of this species. It turned out that this species is characterized by sexual dimorphism: males have less developed tubercles on elytra than females (Fig. 3). The photographs of the habitus (Fig. 4) and the aedeagus (Figs 27, 28) are given for the first time.

Distribution. China [Tan et al., 2005; Moseyko, 2024], Thailand (new record).

Iphimoides pallidulus (Jacoby, 1889)

(Fig. 5)

Material. 3♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1100m N 18°56'48.3", E 99°21'22.4" 10.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but “11.V.2024”; 3♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 16.V.2024”; 2♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024”.

Notes. This species was confused with *Iphimoides (Clisitherella) suturalis* Pic, 1982, considered its synonym for some time and discussed in detail by Romantsov and Moseyko [2019]. *Iphimoides pallidulus* was described from Myanmar, its records from China and Vietnam [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1961] may in fact refer to *I. suturalis*.

Distribution. Myanmar (Tenasserim) [Jacoby, 1908], Southern China (?), Vietnam (?) [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1961; Moseyko, 2024], Northern Thailand (new record).

Pagria vietnamica Moseyko et Medvedev, 2005

(Fig. 6)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1121m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°56'58", E 99°20'54" 10.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 3♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1105-1099m, N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 11.V.2024”; 3♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1105-1108m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 12.V.2024”; 2♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34", N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 15.V.2024”.

Notes. Oriental species of *Pagria* Lefèvre, 1884 were reviewed and keyed by Moseyko and Medvedev [2005]. In the description of this species, they mentioned unicolour yellow upper side of the body, sometimes with darkened suture. The characters of the specimens that I've collected in Thailand fully correspond to all the characters of this species. All males also have unicolour yellow body, but females can have blurred dark spots on the pronotum and the elytra as well as black suture. These spots may be developed to varying degrees from barely noticeable smears to rather large indistinct spots.

Distribution. Vietnam [Moseyko, Medvedev, 2005], Northern Thailand [Moseyko, 2012].

Parascela hirsuta (Jacoby, 1908)

(Fig. 7)

Material. 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”.

Notes. The genus *Parascela* Baly, 1878 was comparatively recently reviewed and keyed by Romantsov and Moseyko [2019].

Figs 1–6. Representatives of the subfamilies Criocerinae and Eumolpinae from Thailand, general view.

1 – *Lema mediolineata*, male; 2 – *Lema semiregularis*, male; 3–4 – *Basilepta subtuberosa*: 3 – female, 4 – male; 5 – *Iphimoides pallidulus*, male; 6 – *Pagria vietnamica*, female.

Рис. 1–6. Представители подсемейств Стюсеринае и Еумолпинае из Таиланда, общий вид.

1 – *Lema mediolineata*, самец; 2 – *Lema semiregularis*, самец; 3–4 – *Basilepta subtuberosa*: 3 – самка, 4 – самец; 5 – *Iphimoides pallidulus*, самец; 6 – *Pagria vietnamica*, самка.

Figs 7–15. Leaf beetles from Thailand and Nepal, general view.

7 – *Parascela hirsuta*, female; 8 – *Platycorynus dilaticollis*, male; 9 – *Plagiosterna miniaticollis*, male (Nepal); 10–11 – *P. suwattanae* sp. n., male, holotype: 10 – dorsal view, 11 – ventral view; 12 – *Aplosonyx ornatus*, male; 13 – *Gallerucida moseri*, male; 14 – *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n., male, holotype; 15 – *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., male, holotype.

Рис. 7–15. Листоеды из Таиланда и Непала, общий вид.

7 – *Parascela hirsuta*, самка; 8 – *Platycorynus dilaticollis*, самец; 9 – *Plagiosterna miniaticollis*, самец (Непал); 10–11 – *P. suwattanae* sp. n., самец, голотип: 10 – вид сверху, 11 – вид снизу; 12 – *Aplosonyx ornatus*, самец; 13 – *Gallerucida moseri*, самец; 14 – *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n., самец, голотип; 15 – *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., самец, голотип.

Distribution. Northeast India (Assam), Southern China (Yunnan) [Romantsov, Moseyko, 2019; Moseyko, 2024], Northern Thailand (new record).

Platycorynus dilaticollis
(Jacoby, 1892), **sp. resurr.**
(Fig. 8)

Material. 2♂, 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1040-1019m N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" - N 18°57'26", E 99°20'16 22.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”

Notes. The identification key for Indochinese species of *Platycorynus* Chevrolat, 1836 was published by Kimoto and Gressitt [1982]. In their work *Platycorynus dilaticollis* was synonymized (without any explanation) with *P. chalybeus* Marshall, 1864. Later, all representatives of this genus from Vietnam were reviewed and keyed by Medvedev and Rybakova [1985] where *P. dilaticollis* is considered as a valid species differing from *P. chalybeus* in the convex, rounded on sides pronotum which is about as wide as the elytra at base and in the head with a narrow shallow transverse groove between eyes. In contrast, *P. chalybeus* has the less convex, more or less conical pronotum which is narrower than the elytra at base and the head with a deep transverse groove on the frons between eyes. In the subsequent revision [Tan et al., 2005] *P. dilaticollis* was introduced as a synonym of *P. chalybeus* again. It seems that Tan et al. [2005] did not know about the work of Medvedev and Rybakova. Finally, this species is listed in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera [Moseyko, 2024] as a synonym of *P. chalybeus* (probably based on the mentioned work). I agree with opinion Medvedev and Rybakova and listed this species here as a separate species.

The nominotypical subspecies of this species occurs in Myanmar and Southwestern China while *P. dilaticollis tibialis* L. Medvedev et Rybakova, 1985 was described from Northern Vietnam. It differs from the nominotypical subspecies in pro- and mesotibiae strongly expanded on both outer and inner sides. *Platycorynus dilaticollis dilaticollis* has pro- and mesotibiae expanded only on outer sides. The specimens collected in Northern Thailand belong to the nominotypical subspecies.

Distribution. Myanmar, Southwestern China [Medvedev, Rybakova, 1985], Northern Thailand (new record).

Bathseba tristis (Medvedev, 2001)
(Figs 29, 30)

Material. 3♂, 2♀ (PR), “N Vietnam, Ninh Binh Prov., ~6 km SW Ninh Binh, h~30 m., N 20°13'32", E 105°56'8" 26.IV.2019 P. Romantsov leg.”; 2♀ (PR), the same data, but “27.IV.2019”; 4♂, 4♀ (PR), the same data, but “28.IV.2019”; 3♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1100m N 18°56'48.3", E 99°21'22.4" 10.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but “11.V.2024”; 3♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 16.V.2024”; 2♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024”.

Notes. *Bathseba tristis* was described from Southern Thailand based on one female, later one female was recorded for Northern Thailand [Romantsov, Moseyko, 2016] as well. Examination of my materials from Vietnam (2019) and Northern Thailand (2024) made it possible to

clarify some diagnostic characters and the distribution of this species as well as to give photographs of its aedeagus (Figs 29, 30) for the first time. It has been established that the body colouration of this species is quite stable and resembles one of the holotype, but some specimens have red fulvous pattern on the pronotum and the elytra less contrasting; body length 4.4–4.8 mm in male and 4.6–5.8 mm in female.

Distribution. Thailand [Romantsov, Moseyko, 2016], Vietnam (new record).

Subfamily Chrysomelinae Latreille, 1802 Genus *Plagiosterna* Motschulsky, 1860

The genus *Plagiosterna* Motschulsky, 1860 is very close to *Plagioderia* Chevrolat, 1836 from which it differs in the more elongated body with non-concave epipleura, not furcate tarsomere III and in convexity along lateral margins of the elytra. Recently, several works [Ge et al., 2008; Sprecher-Uebersax, Daccordi, 2016a, b] have been published in which a few species new to science were described as well as some important comments on their taxonomy have been made based on the study of type material and some species have been transferred from one genus to another.

Plagiosterna suwattanae sp. n.
(Figs 10, 11, 31, 32)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1108m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 12.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”. Paratype: 1♂ (PR), the same data as in the holotype.

Description. Holotype. Antennae, legs and underside brown. Head and pronotum reddish brown. Scutellum black, elytra metallic green. Body length 6.9 mm. General view as in Fig. 10.

Body moderately oblong, slightly widened in middle, 1.41 times as long as wide. Head lustrous, labrum with broadly concave anterior margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate, lustrous with several setae along margins. Penultimate maxillary palpomere very slightly expanded, apical palpomere rather long (slightly longer than previous one) with oblique truncated apex. Frontoclypeus with almost flat and impunctate clypeal part; frons slightly convex with almost straight anterior and rounded posterior margins, surface covered by rather dense punctures and fine microsculpture with thin groove in middle. Frontal tubercles slightly convex, transverse triangular, almost touching each other with narrow triangular angles but distinctly separated with thin groove; distinctly delimited anteriorly and poorly delimited posteriorly. Surface of frontal tubercles shining and impunctate. Eyes rather large but slightly convex, 1.67 times as long as wide; interocular space 2.67 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex rather densely covered with moderately large punctures, surface widely depressed before frontal tubercles with narrow groove in middle. Antennae robust, about 2.8 times shorter than body length. Antennomere I large, stout, antennomere II shortest, antennomere III just little shorter than antennomere I. Antennomeres I–IV lustrous with sparse erected setae. Antennomeres V–XI matte, their rugose surfaces covered with short adpressed setae and with separate erected longer setae on anterior margin. Antennomere XI with triangular apex. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 13 : 7 : 12 : 9 : 8.5 : 8 : 8.5 : 9 : 10 : 9 : 12, width ratio as 9 : 5.5 : 5 : 6.5 : 7 : 7 : 8 : 9 : 9 : 9.

Pronotum transverse, 2.06 times as wide as long (widest at basal third); at level of its posterior angles 1.38 times narrower

than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight; basal margin almost straight near lateral angles but with middle of pronotal base distinctly protruded opposite scutellum; lateral margins rounded. Anterior and lateral margins distinctly bordered, posterior margins thinner bordered. Anterior angles rounded; posterior angles obtuse. All angles without setigerous pore. Pronotal surface moderately lustrous, punctured with moderately dense, not large punctures and has indistinct microsculpture; with indistinct weak depression in middle of anterior third.

Scutellum triangular (1.37 times as wide as long) with rounded apex; its surface lustrous with microsculpture more developed along base. Elytra 1.1 times as long as wide, with rounded lateral margins, widest around middle. Elytral surface with not very deep depressions: two at base (one between internal margin of humeral callus and anterior margin of elytra; another depression between latter one and scutellum) and longitudinal depression near lateral margin below humeral tubercles; moderately densely and confusedly covered with distinct punctures with slightly convex interstices. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura not concave. Epipleural surface lustrous and almost impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs robust, bare over most of surface and with short setae only near apex. All tibiae with two long keels (higher in distal part) along entire length on upperside. Protibiae strongly, mesotibiae moderately, and metatibiae very slightly curved; all tibiae without spurs. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 12 : 9 : 12 : 23; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 14 : 1 : 17. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 14 : 18 : 14 : 23; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 14 : 12 : 18. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 15 : 8 : 15 : 23; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 14 : 11 : 17. Tarsomere III shortly incised in the middle; tarsal claws simple, separate.

Ventral side (Fig. 11) very sparsely punctured with punctures bearing a short curved seta. Prosternal process strongly protruding between procoxal cavities, enlarged at apex which enters to hollow of mesoventrite. Surface of prosternal process strongly convex along entire length forming rather high carina. Procoxal cavities open posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite simple. Pygidium convex with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 31, 32) about 2.8 times as long as wide, widest at base, then gently narrowing to triangular apex with rounded tip. In lateral view curved with tip turned up. Ventral side of aedeagus slightly concave. Length of aedeagus about 1.8 mm, width 0.65 mm.

Paratype. In colouration and morphological features this male is very similar to the holotype. It had the similar shape of the aedeagus which was later lost during examination of this specimen. Body length 7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. This new species belongs to the group of species from Indochina with brown body and metallic elytra, which also includes *Plagiosterna acuticollis* Sprecher-Uebersax et Daccordi, 2016, *P. aeneipennis* (Baly, 1859), *P. confusa* Sprecher-Uebersax et Daccordi, 2016, *P. marginipennis* (Jacoby, 1889), *P. miniaticollis* (Hope, 1831) and *P. seximpressa* (Chen, 1931). *Plagiosterna suwattanae* sp. n. can be easily distinguished from them in entirely yellow antennae, lateral margins of the pronotum rounded, strongly curved protibiae and strongly convex prosternal process along its entire length. In contrast, other species of this group have black or blackened apical antennomeres, almost straight or less curved protibiae and lateral margins of pronotum, weakly convex prosternal process. *Plagiosterna confusa* and *P. miniaticollis* (Fig. 9) having slightly curved protibiae and lateral margins of the pronotum (but less than in *P. suwattanae* sp. n.) are the most similar to those in the new species. However, both these species have other body colouration with black apical

antennomeres (*P. confusa* also with green scutellum) and different shape of the aedeagus with a less curved upwardly tip.

Etymology. This new species is named in honour of Suwattana Nasatain who helped me with logistics and accommodation arrangement during field work in Thailand in 2024.

Subfamily Galerucinae Latreille, 1802

Aplosonyx ornatus (Jacoby, 1892)

(Fig. 12)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 15.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024”; 2♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 21.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 25.V.2024”.

Distribution. China (Yunnan), Myanmar, Laos [Kimoto, 1989; Feng et al., 2023; Bemeen et al., 2024], Thailand (new record).

Gallerucida moseri Weise, 1922

(Fig. 13)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1226-1400m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 23.V.2024”; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 26.V.2024”.

Distribution. China, Vietnam [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015], Thailand (new record).

Hoplosaenidea aerosa (Laboissière, 1933)

Material. 3♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1099m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1288-1246 m, N 18°56'46", E 99°21'2" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 14.V.2024”; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024”; 1♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 21.V.2024”.

Distribution. China (Yunnan), Laos [Bezděk, 2009], Thailand (new record).

Kanarella unicolor Jacoby, 1896

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 15.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024”; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024”; 1♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1045-1015m N 18°57'8.5", E 99°20'42" - N 18°57'22", E 99°20'24" 20.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 21.V.2024”; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1226-1400m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 23.V.2024; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but “24.V.2024”.

Distribution. India, Nepal, China (Yunnan), Laos, Vietnam [Kimoto, 1989; Medvedev, 2019], Thailand (new record).

Genus *Luperocella* Jakoby, 1900

The genus *Luperocella* was established by Jacoby [1900] with one species *Luperocella hirsuta* Jacoby, 1900. Later, Maulik [1936] described the genus *Alafia* Maulik, 1936 and transferred there *Galerucella albopilosa* Jacoby, 1892, *G. melancholica* Jacoby, 1889 and *G. submetallescens* Baly, 1879. Then Aslam [1972] synonymized *Alafia* with *Luperocella*. Finally, Medvedev [2001] synonymized *L. hirsuta* with *L. albopilosa*. Until now, the distribution of representatives of this genus was limited to Assam and Myanmar only. During fieldwork in Thailand 2024, I've collected a rather large series of representatives of this genus, belonging to a new species. Thanks to the kindness of J. Bezděk I was able to study photographs of the type specimens of all known species of *Luperocella*. This made it possible to describe one new species, introduce taxonomic changes to some known species, and compile the first identification key for all known species of this little-studied genus.

Members of the genus *Luperocella*, belonging to the tribe Galerucini, can be easily distinguished from other Galerucinae genera in following characters: body densely covered with long erect setae; vertex wrinkled; pronotum with anterior and lateral margins unbordered, pronotal surface with four depressions (one deep lateral depression on each side and two smaller ones on longitudinal middle line of which anterior depression is usually larger than posterior one); claws bifid; procoxal cavities open; last abdominal ventrite without incisions.

Medvedev [2001] synonymized *L. hirsuta* sp. **resurr.** with *L. albopilosa*, suggesting that these species are identical. I was able to study photographs of the type specimens of both these species, which are also completely consistent with the original descriptions [Jacoby, 1892, 1900]. After examination of these photographs I am sure that these are two different species which may be distinguished by the characters given in a key below.

Luperocella thailandica sp. n. (Figs 14, 33, 34, 47)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.". Paratypes: 1♀ (JB), "NW Thailand, 19.9N, 97 59E Mae Hon Son, 1991 Ban Huai Po, 1600-2000m 9-16.5., L. Dembický leg."; 1♂ (JB), "THAI, N, Mae Hon Son prov., SE of Soppong, 1500m, 19°27'N, 98°20'E, 23-27.v.1999, M. Řiha leg."; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1108m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 12.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1288-1246 m, N 18°56'46", E 99°21'2" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 14.V.2024"; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 15.V.2024"; 3♂, 4♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), same locality and collector, but "h~1105m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 18.V.2024"; 4♀ (PR), the same date as in holotype; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1045-1015m N 18°57'8.5", E 99°20'42" - N 18°57'22", E 99°20'24" 20.V.2024"; 2♂, 6♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 21.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "1226-1400m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 23.V.2024"; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 25.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same data, but "28.V.2024".

Description. Holotype. Antennae black. Head red-brown with large black spot on vertex; pronotum, scutellum and elytra black. Ventral side black with last abdominal ventrite brown. Legs black. Body length 6.7 mm. General view as in Fig. 14.

Body oblong, 2.25 times as long as wide, very slightly widened behind middle; densely covered with rather long (longest on elytra), erected silver setae. Head slightly lustrous, labrum with almost straight apical margin. Labrum surface convex and lustrous with several punctures bearing long pale seta. Penultimate maxillary palpomere slightly expanded; apical palpomere just slightly shorter but distinctly narrower than previous one, conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus convex anteriorly; forming posteriorly moderately wide and almost flat ridge in interantennal space; surface of frontoclypeus impunctate but with microsculpture and sparse setae. Genae rather long, just slightly shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles large, moderately convex, almost square, located close to each other, but distinct separated with deep groove, not very distinctly delimited posteriorly with thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles rather rugose with several punctures bearing long pale seta. Eyes small, slightly convex, oval (1.2 times as long as wide); interocular space 2.36 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex slightly convex without longitudinal groove in middle; vertex surface rather rugose with moderately dense sub-erect setae. Antennae rather long, 1.35 times shorter than body length. Antennomere I moderately large, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–VIII slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres IX–XI almost cylindrical; last antennomere with sharp apex. Antennomeres I–IV lustrous covered with longer semi-adpressed setae; rest antennomeres matt, covered with shorter semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 28 : 11 : 17 : 18 : 19 : 17 : 17 : 15 : 16 : 16 : 24, width ratio as 9.5 : 6 : 7 : 7 : 8 : 8 : 8 : 8 : 7 : 6.5 : 6.

Pronotum transverse, 1.58 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles 1.62 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin slightly concave; posterior margin almost straight; lateral margins uneven, angularly widened in anterior third. Anterior and lateral margins unbordered; posterior margin indistinctly and thinly bordered. Anterior and posterior angles tooth-shaped, slightly protruding, at apex bearing long pale seta. Pronotal surface uneven with four depressions: one deep lateral depression on each side and two much smaller ones on longitudinal middle line (anterior depression slightly larger than posterior one); densely punctured, with convex narrow interstices and long erect setae.

Scutellum triangular with rounded apex, 1.62 times as wide as long; its surface lustrous, slightly wrinkled, covered with large and small punctures. Elytra 1.55 times as long as wide; slightly widened behind middle with rounded apex. Elytra without subbasal depression. Elytral surface distinctly wrinkled, confusedly covered with distinct punctures with convex interstices (in places merging into short ridges). Humeral calli developed. Epipleura not wide at anterior third, then gradually narrowing and disappearing approximately at level of posterior third. Epipleural surface uneven, slightly wrinkled with sparse, short, semi-adpressed setae. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, rather densely covered with long semi-erect setae. Pro- and mesotibiae almost straight, metatibiae slightly curved; all tibiae without spurs. Each tarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomeres III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 19 : 10 : 9 : 23; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 8 : 8 : 11. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 17 : 10 : 9 : 23; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 8 : 8 : 11. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 20 : 10 : 10 : 24; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 7 : 6.5 : 11. Metatarsomere I straight, slightly widened at apex; about as long as two next tarsomeres combined. Tarsal claws bifid.

Ventral side sparsely covered with adpressed setae and small punctures. Prosternal process reduced to narrow keel which reaches just about middle of intercoxal space. Procoxal cavities

open posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite with shallow longitudinal triangular depression in apical half; apical margin without incises, but with small notch at apex. Pygidium convex, triangular with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 33, 34) about 6 times as long as wide, slightly widened before apex. Apex of aedeagus narrow triangular. In lateral view aedeagus slightly sinuous with tip bent upwards. Ventral side of aedeagus convex without depressions. Length of aedeagus about 2.25 mm, width 0.37 mm.

Paratypes. Males are similar to the holotype; pronotum 1.55–1.63 times as wide as long; body length 6.5–6.6 mm. Females are similar to males, but have slightly more transverse pronotum (about 1.7–1.74 times as wide as long) and last abdominal ventrite simple without depression; body length 7.3–7.5 mm. Specimens from Mae Hong Son Province have pronotum black with widely blurred red-brown sides. Spermatheca as in Fig. 47. Length of spermatheca 0.5 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n. is closest to *L. albopilosa* but differs in legs entirely black, antennomeres III and IV equal and in the somewhat more transverse pronotum which is 1.55–1.74 times as wide as long. *Luperocella albopilosa* has legs partly testaceous, antennomere III shorter than IV and the pronotum somewhat narrower (1.45–1.55 times as wide as long). See also a key.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to Thailand where the type series have been collected.

Key to the species of the genus *Luperocella* Jacoby, 1900

- 1(2). Antennae robust, reach about half of body. Body black. Body length 6.3–7 mm. Myanmar *L. melancholica*
- 2(1). Antennae slender, longer than half length of body.
- 3(4). Pronotum coarsely punctured. Body dorsally black with slight metallic tint, legs and antennae black (two apical antennomeres and edges of last abdominal ventrite may be brownish). Body length about 8.5 mm. India (Assam) *L. submetallescens*
- 4(3). Punctuation of pronotum smaller, less rough. Body not entirely black (dorsal side and/or legs partly testaceous).
- 5(8). Legs partly testaceous. Species from Myanmar.
- 6(7). Head testaceous with a large black spot on vertex; pronotum and elytra from dark brown to black with faint purplish sheen on elytra; femora testaceous, femora-tibial articulation, tibiae and tarsi black. Antennomere IV longer than III. Body length 6.3–7 mm *L. albopilosa*
- 7(6). Body dorsally black with distinct metallic bronzy sheen; legs testaceous, femora-tibial articulation and tarsi black. Antennomeres III and IV equal. Body length 6–6.5 mm *L. hirsuta*
- 8(5). Head testaceous with a large black spot on vertex; pronotum, elytra and legs black. Antennomere III and IV equal. Body length 6.3–7.5 mm. Thailand *L. thailandica* sp. n.

Genus *Paleosepharia* Laboissière, 1936

There are many papers devoted to the systematics of the genus *Paleosepharia* Laboissière, 1936. Species of this genus from Indochina were reviewed and keyed by

Medvedev [2014]. There are also identification keys to *Paleosepharia* species in many works [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Mohamedsaid, 1996; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Lee, 2018]. In addition, special mention deserves the work of Mohamedsaid and Furth [2011] about secondary sexual characters in males of Galerucinae, which includes this genus. Several recently published works provide descriptions of the taxa new for science or with species recorded for the first time, as well as taxonomic remarks to already known species from the region under consideration [Mohamedsaid, Constant, 2007; Medvedev, 2013; Rizki et al., 2014, 2016; Nguyen, Gómez-Zurita, 2017, etc.].

Paleosepharia magnitarsis sp. n. (Figs 15, 35–37)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 26.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.;"

Description. Holotype. Antennae brown with three first antennomeres light-brown and apical part of last three antennomeres darkened. Head brown with 2 oblique yellow stripes; pronotum and scutellum brown; elytra brown with indistinct lighter areas visible along basal and lateral margins as well as in central part of elytral disk where they look like unclear oblique stripes from humeral tubercles to suture, epipleura reddish brown in basal part. Ventral side brown except metaventrite, last abdominal ventrite and pygidium red-brown; legs light-brown with tibiae and tarsi darkened. Body length 6.1 mm. General view as in Fig. 15.

Body rather oblong, about 2.12 times as long as wide, widest approximately at level of apical third. Head lustrous, labrum with slightly convex apical margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate, lustrous with several setae along apical margin. Penultimate maxillary palpomere not expanded; apical palpomere long, not narrower than previous one, conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus slightly convex, impunctate but with microsculpture, forming moderately wide and slightly convex ridge in interantennal space. Genae very short, about 8.5 times shorter than transverse diameter of eye and about 10.5 times shorter than longitudinal diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, triangular with slightly produced inner anterior angles, located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinct separated by thin deep groove, distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles impunctate but with indistinct microsculpture. Eyes large, strongly convex, oval (1.24 times as long as wide); interocular space 1.18 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex without longitudinal groove in middle or depression before frontal tubercles; surface of vertex sparsely covered with very small, microscopic punctures. Antennae long, slightly longer than body length. Antennomere I moderately large, club-shaped, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–VII slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VIII–XI almost cylindrical; last antennomere with sharp tip. Antennomeres I–III almost glabrous, other ones not very densely covered with short semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 27 : 8 : 11 : 25 : 30 : 29 : 28 : 26 : 27 : 26 : 29, width ratio as 7 : 4.5 : 5 : 6 : 5.5 : 5.5 : 5 : 4.5 : 4 : 4 : 3.5.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.92 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles 1.43 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin slightly concave; posterior margin convex; lateral margins very weakly rounded, barely noticeable notched before anterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered, lateral margins distinctly bordered; posterior margin distinctly bordered near posterior angles but not bordered opposite of scutellum. Anterior angles almost rectangular, slightly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly

Figs 16–26. Leaf beetles from Thailand, general view and details of structure.

16 – *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., male, holotype; 17 – *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n., male, holotype; 18–21 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* sp. n., male, holotype: 18 – habitus, 19 – head, 20 – metatibia, dorsal view, 21 – metatibia, lateral view; 22 – *Hyphasis limbatipennis*, female; 23 – *Laboissierea minuta*, female; 24 – *Xuthea orientalis*, male; 25 – *Prionispa cheni*, male; 26 – *Prionispa opacipennis*, male.

Рис. 16–26. Листоеды из Таиланда, общий вид и детали строения.

16 – *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., самец, голотип; 17 – *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n., самец, голотип; 18–21 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* sp. n., самец, голотип: 18 – внешний вид, 19 – голова, 20 – задняя голень, вид сверху, 21 – задняя голень, вид сбоку; 22 – *Hyphasis limbatipennis*, самка; 23 – *Laboissierea minuta*, самка; 24 – *Xuthea orientalis*, самец; 25 – *Prionispa cheni*, самец; 26 – *Prionispa opacipennis*, самец.

Figs 27–48. Leaf beetles from Thailand and China, aedeagi and spermathecae.

27–46 – aedeagi; 47–48 – spermathecae. 27–28 – *Basilepta subtuberosa*; 29–30 – *Tricliona tristis*; 31–32 – *Plagiosterna suwattanae* sp. n., holotype; 33–34, 47 – *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n.: 33–34 – holotype, 47 – paratype; 35–37 – *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., holotype; 38 – *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., holotype; 39–41, 48 – *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n.: 39–41 – holotype, 48 – paratype; 42–43 – *Pyrrhalta kwangtungensis*, paratype (China); 44–46 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* sp. n., holotype. 27, 29, 31, 33, 36, 41, 42, 44, 47, 48 – dorsal view; 28, 30, 32, 34, 37, 40, 43, 45 – lateral view; 35, 38, 46 – ventral view.

Рис. 27–48. Листоеды из Таиланда и Китая, эдеагусы и сперматеки.

27–46 – эдеагусы; 47–48 – сперматеки. 27–28 – *Basilepta subtuberosa*; 29–30 – *Tricliona tristis*; 31–32 – *Plagiosterna suwattanae* sp. n., голотип; 33–34, 47 – *Luperocella thailandica* sp. n.: 33–34 – голотип, 47 – паратип; 35–37 – *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n., голотип; 38 – *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n., голотип; 39–41, 48 – *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n.: 39–41 – голотип, 48 – паратип; 42–43 – *Pyrrhalta kwangtungensis*, паратип (Китай); 44–46 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* sp. n., голотип. 27, 29, 31, 33, 36, 41, 42, 44, 47, 48 – вид сверху; 28, 30, 32, 34, 37, 40, 43, 45 – вид сбоку; 35, 38, 46 – вид снизу.

protruding. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta, lateral margin with several additional short setae. Pronotal surface lustrous with wide, transverse, very feeble depression on each side of middle; densely (but more sparsely in depressed areas) punctured with small punctures.

Scutellum triangular with sharp apex, about 1.5 times as wide as long; its surface lustrous without punctures but with microsculpture. Elytra 1.67 times as long as wide; slightly widened behind middle; its apex not sharply truncated. Elytra without sub-basal depression or modified area; just very slightly, almost unnoticeably depressed along suture near scutellum. Elytral surface densely and confusedly punctured with distinct punctures, interstices slightly convex. Humeral calli developed. Epipleura wide at anterior third, then gradually narrowing towards apex and reaching inner elytral angles. Epipleura turned outward at truncate apex so their ventral margin visible from above. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. Protibiae slightly curved without spur, mesotibiae almost straight with short spur, metatibiae slightly curved and noticeably widened at apex with long spur. Protarsomere I enlarged: swollen at underside, flattened at underside (Fig. 15), much wider than tarsomere III. Meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 18 : 9 : 11 : 25; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 12 : 5 : 9. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 29 : 10 : 7 : 15; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 4.5 : 5 : 9. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 47 : 10 : 6 : 15; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 5 : 5 : 8. Metatarsomere I straight with almost parallel margins, about 1.7 times as long as next three tarsomeres combined and 2.17 times shorter than length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side sparsely covered with adpressed setae and small punctures. Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel barely visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed; middle lobe rectangular with slightly rounded lateral angles, longer than lateral lobes, its surface with short and thin longitudinal groove in apical part. Pygidium convex, triangular with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 35–37) moderately wide in basal half (with maximum width 0.42 mm) then narrowing towards apex (with minimal width before apex 0.05 mm), apex anchor-shaped with three teeth (maximum apex width at level of lateral teeth 0.225 mm). Apex of aedeagus deeply thinly incised. Sub-apical narrow portion with longitudinal groove in dorsal view. In lateral view aedeagus sinuous and strongly bent down (at angle almost 90°) before apex. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal half and smooth in other portion. Length of aedeagus about 2.8 mm, width 0.42 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n. belongs to the species group with unmodified elytra in male. Members of this group often have shallow depressions on the pronotum. This new species is easily distinguished from other members of this group in brown with indistinct white areas colouration of the dorsal side of body and in unique shape of the aedeagus (anchor-shaped apex in dorsal view and strongly bent down before apex in lateral view). In addition, this species is easily distinguished from all congeners in greatly expanded male protarsomere I. Such sexual dimorphism is not characteristic of other *Paleosepharia* species, both sexes of which have normally wide tarsi. As for *P. tibialis* Chen et Jiang, 1984 from China (Guangxi), it is described based on a single female. This species also has brown body with tibiae and tarsi black, similar colouration of the ventral side, large size of body (7 mm), but differs (according to its original description and study of photographs of the holotype) in scutellum

black and the pronotum without trace of any depressions. *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* sp. n. has brown scutellum and the pronotum with lateral margins very weakly and evenly rounded, pronotal surface with wide, transverse, very feeble depression on each side of middle.

Etymology. The name of the new species is a Latinize adjective derived from magnus “large” and tarsis “tarsi”, to reflect the enlarge protarsomere I.

Paleosepharia rubroapicata sp. n.
(Figs 16, 38)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 21.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”

Description. Holotype. Antennae brown with tip of last antennomere darkened, head black. Pronotum and scutellum red, elytra brown with red apex. Ventral side red-brown, apices of abdomen and pygidium black; legs brown with femora red-brown. Body length 4.6 mm. General view as in Fig. 16.

Body not very elongate, about 1.92 times as long as wide, widest behind middle. Head lustrous, labrum with slightly convex apical margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate, lustrous with several setae along apical margin. Penultimate maxillary palpomere very slightly expanded, apical palpomere rather long (barely shorter than previous one), conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus very wide and convex, almost impunctate, forming wide convex ridge in interantennal space. Genae very short, about 7.5 times shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, subquadrate; connected to each other, not delimited anteriorly (connected with interantennal ridge), poorly delimited posteriorly with thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles lustrous with indistinct microsculpture. Eyes large, strongly convex, almost round; interocular space about as wide as diameter of eye. Vertex convex with thin longitudinal groove in middle and with depression before frontal tubercles; vertex surface sparsely covered with small punctures and indistinct microsculpture. Antennae moderately long, about 1.1 times shorter than body length. Antennomere I large, stout, slightly curved, club-shaped, antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–V slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VI–X almost cylindrical. Antennomere XI slightly widened in apical quarter, apex triangular with sharp tip. Antennomeres I–III almost glabrous, other ones not densely covered with short semi-adpressed setae and with separate protruding setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 22 : 7 : 9 : 11 : 19 : 19 : 19 : 19 : 18 : 16 : 18, width ratio as 5 : 3.5 : 4 : 7 : 4 : 4 : 3.5 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.75 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles 1.3 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight; posterior margin very slightly convex; lateral margins weakly rounded, slightly notched before anterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered; posterior margin thin, lateral margins distinctly bordered. Anterior angles almost rectangular, slightly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta, lateral margins with several additional short setae. Pronotal surface lustrous with sparse, very small punctures; without traces of any depressions.

Scutellum triangular with sharp apex, about as wide as long; its surface lustrous with very small punctures and microsculpture. Elytra 1.44 times as long as wide; relatively narrow at base, gradually widened (widest at level of posterior third) and then more abruptly narrowed towards sharply truncate apex. Elytra without sub-basal depression, but with modified area in form of wide, not deep impression along suture limited outside with distinct long keels, almost parallel to suture. Almost all elytral surface very densely

and confusedly covered with distinct punctures with slightly convex interstices. Punctures in modified elytral area sparser and smaller. Humeral calli weakly developed. Epipleura moderately wide at anterior quarter, then gradually narrowing toward truncate apex and disappearing not far from inner elytral angles. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. All tibiae almost straight, very slightly widened at apex; with spurs (longest ones on metatibiae) at apex. Pro-, meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 10 : 6 : 5 : 9; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 16 : 6 : 5 : 11; of metatarsomeres I–III and V are as 36 : 7 : 5 : 12. Metatarsomere I straight with almost parallel margins; approximately twice as long as three next tarsomeres combined and slightly longer than half length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side covered with pale adpressed setae (denser on ventrites of metathorax). Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel barely visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed, middle lobe rectangular slightly longer than lateral lobes, its surface with wide longitudinal triangular depression in apical part. Pygidium convex, triangular with widely rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Fig. 38) with broken apical part. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal half and with shallow longitudinal depression in other visible part. Length of aedeagus (excluding broken part) about 1.75 mm, width 0.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n. differs from other congeners in its colouration: head black, pronotum red, elytra brown with red apex, metasternum and abdomen red-brown, apices of abdomen and pygidium black; as well as in the unusual shape of modified area on the male elytra. This new species is similar to *P. membranacea* Medvedev, 2001 and *P. buonloica* Medvedev, 2014, but the first species has the black pronotum, and the latter one has the entirely brown elytra; in addition, both species have the male elytra without modified area. *Paleosepharia rubroapicata* sp. n. has a wide modified elytral area, almost parallel to suture and limited outside with distinct long keels. The majority of congeners has modified elytral area in the shape of various impressions (drop-like, spindle-form, Y-form); if this impression is more or less parallel to suture (in *P. lingulata* Chen et Jiang, 1984, *P. subsuturalis* Medvedev, 2009, *P. suturalis* Medvedev, 2009 and *P. vietnamica* Medvedev, 2004), it is much narrower than in *P. rubroapicata* sp. n.

Etymology. The name of this new species refers to its colouration with red elytral apex.

Genus *Pyrrhalta* Joannis, 1865

There are many works devoted to the systematics of the genus *Pyrrhalta* Joannis, 1865; here I mention only ones that contain the most important keys for identification of the species of this genus from Indochina [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015, etc.]. It should be mentioned separately the species catalogue of *Pyrrhalta* of the World [Xue, Yang, 2010]. Traditionally, the genera *Pyrrhalta* and *Menippus* Clark, 1864 were distinguished by a degree of closure of the procoxal cavity, which is open in *Pyrrhalta* and closed in *Menippus*. This character is commonly used to delimit tribes and subtribes in the Chrysomelidae, but some genera have diverse cavity closure. In the revision of *Menippus* from

Australia [Reid, Nally, 2008: 88] authors mentioned: “the generic keys to Galerucinae of south-east Asia (Kimoto, 1989) and New Guinea (Shute, 1983) fail to identify most Australian species as *Menippus* because this trait varies among Australian representatives of the genus”. In the same work they wrote that *Menippus* easily distinguish from the genera with the pubescent dorsal surface, green or brown colouration and partly depressed pronotal disc by the following [Reid, Nally, 2008: 89]: “green colour ephemeral, absent in dead specimens; pronotum entirely pubescent and not transversely depressed; elytral epipleura abruptly contracted between base and hind coxa; claws bifid”. However, in my opinion, *Menippus* and *Pyrrhalta* cannot be distinguished based on these characters. The latter has similar characteristics, including various different shape of epipleura. In subsequent works devoted to this genus [Lee et al., 2012; Suenaga et al., 2017] only the question of the identity of the genera *Menippus* and *Issikia* Chujo, 1961 is considered, and as for distinguishing the genus *Menippus* from other genera, a reference to the work of Reid and Nally is used. In my opinion the question of the difference between these two genera still remains open and requires further study.

Pyrrhalta khuntanensis sp. n.

(Figs 17, 39–41, 48)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 16.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.” Paratype: 1♀ (ZIN), the same data as in holotype, but “15.V.2024”.

Description. Holotype. Antennae brown; dorsal side of body grey-brown, pronotum with oval black spot on each side; legs brown with black femora-tibial articulation. Ventral side grey-brown with abdomen brown. Body length 8 mm. General view as in Fig. 17.

Body moderately oblong, slightly widened posteriorly, about 2.1 times as long as wide. Head densely punctured, labrum with slightly convex apical margin. Labrum surface moderately convex, impunctate, lustrous with several setae along apical margin and with denser and longer setae along connection with frontoclypeus. Penultimate maxillary palpomere almost not expanded (only slightly wider than previous palpomere), apical palpomere long (about as long as previous one), conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus wide, rather convex with setae along sides, its surface lustrous above but with finely wrinkled sculpture on lateral slopes. Genae about 2.8 times shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Space between antennal sockets with rather convex ridge. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, subquadrate; narrowly separated to each other with thin groove, distinctly delimited anteriorly with wide groove, poorly delimited posteriorly with thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles shining, distinctly punctured, with several short semi-erect setae. Eyes large, strongly convex, very slightly oval (1.05 times as long as wide); interocular space moderately wide (1.35 times as wide as diameter of eye). Vertex rather densely covered with moderately large punctures and semi-erect setae. Antennae moderately robust, about 1.7 times shorter than body length. Antennomere I large, stout, slightly curved, club-shaped, antennomere II short, slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres III–VIII widened at apex. Antennomeres IX and X almost cylindrical. Antennomere XI slightly widened in apical quarter, apex triangular with sharp tip. Antennomeres I–III sparsely, other ones densely covered with short semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 10 : 5 : 17 : 21 : 21 : 20 : 20 : 18 : 18 : 18 : 21, width ratio as 8 : 6 : 6.5 : 7 : 7 : 7 : 6.5 : 6 : 5.5 : 5.

Pronotum transverse, about 2 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles 1.35 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin very slightly concave; posterior margin very slightly convex; lateral margins sinuous, protrude roundly to side at level of anterior third and very slightly notched before anterior angles. Anterior and posterior margins unbordered, lateral margins bordered. Anterior angles almost rectangular, slightly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. Posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta, anterior angles without setae, but lateral margin with several short setae. Pronotal surface moderately lustrous, punctured with dense, rather large punctures and covered with semi-adpressed silvery setae; very slightly depressed near middle of each side.

Scutellum triangular with rounded apex, about as wide as long; its surface lustrous with dense, small punctures and rather long adpressed silvery setae. Elytra 1.55 times as long as wide, widened at posterior third. Elytral surface without subbasal depression; very densely and confusedly covered with distinct punctures (with very narrow slightly convex interstices) and silvery setae. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura moderately wide at anterior quarter, then gradually narrowing and disappearing in apical quarter. Epipleural surface lustrous, impunctate, but with microsculpture. Macropterous.

Legs moderately robust, covered with pale semi-adpressed setae. All tibiae almost straight, slightly widened at apex; without spurs. Protarsomere I very slightly enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, noticeably narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 10 : 5 : 5 : 8; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 8 : 6 : 5 : 11; of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 7 : 6 : 11. Metatarsomere I almost straight, slightly widened at apex; slightly shorter than length of metatarsomeres I–II combined. Tarsal claws bifid.

Ventral side covered with pale adpressed setae (denser on ventrites of metathorax). Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel barely visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities rather widely open posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite with distinct broadly triangular emargination about 1/3 as long as ventrite. Pygidium convex, triangular with widely rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Fig 39–41) about 5.5 times as long as wide, widest at middle part, then gently narrows to triangular apex. In lateral view sinuous, with tip bent to side. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal half and with shallow longitudinal lanceolate depression in apical half. Length of aedeagus about 2.3 mm, width 0.42 mm.

Paratype. Female is similar to male, but last abdominal ventrite without emargination. Spermatheca as in Fig. 48. Length of spermatheca 0.72 mm. Body length 8.5 mm.

Differential diagnosis. Thanks to the kindness of J. Bezděk I checked the photographs of the habitus of the allotype as well as the habitus and the aedeagus (Figs 42, 43) of one paratype of *P. kwangtungensis* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963, which I believe is most similar to the species described here. These images completely correspond to the original description including the drawing of the aedeagus. Differences between these two species are given on the basis of the above-mentioned description and photographs.

Pyrrhalta kwangtungensis from South China (Guangdong) has the pronotum with similar spots and legs with black femora-tibial articulation, but differs in the paler body colouration (pronotum and elytra ochraceous or yellowish-brown without any metallic tint) and in the shape of the aedeagus (slightly arched in lateral view; gradually and slightly widening to a short distance before apex in dorsal view). *Pyrrhalta khuntanensis* sp. n. has the pronotum and the elytra grey brown with weak metallic bronze tint and the aedeagus slightly sinuous in lateral view, not widening before apex in dorsal view.

Body shape and colouration of *P. khuntanensis* sp. n. is also similar to species of the genus *Menippus*, especially ones having back spots on the pronotum (*M. issikii* (Chûjô, 1961) and *M. hsuehleeae* Lee, Bezděk et Suenaga, 2012). But these species differ in darkened antennae and apex of tibiae as well as in the different shape of aedeagi.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the collecting locality situated on the Khun Tan Range.

Genus *Sinoluperoides* Kimoto, 1989

The genus *Sinoluperoides* was established by Kimoto [1989] for four species: *S. maculatus* Kimoto, 1989 (type species), *S. major* Kimoto, 1989 and *S. marginalis* Kimoto, 1989 from Vietnam, and *S. antennatus* Kimoto, 1989 from Laos. Later, Medvedev [2012] described the fifth species *S. costatus* Medvedev, 2012 from Vietnam. Thus, this genus currently comprises five species. *Sinoluperoides* can be distinguished from other Galerucinae genera by the following combination of characters: body elongate, antennal insertions and frontal tubercles widely separated by frons; labrum bilobed apically; genae very narrow; antenna with third segment distinctly longer than second; prothorax with depression in basal third, pronotal anterior margin unbordered, lateral and posterior margins distinctly bordered; elytra irregularly punctured, epipleura wide at base and gradually narrowed to apex; prosternal process not elevated between anterior coxae; procoxal cavities closed posteriorly; meso- and metatibiae with distinct spur at apex, metatarsomere I longer than length of metatarsomeres I–II combined, tarsal claws appendiculate; last abdominal ventrite trilobed. Among other genera *Sinoluperoides* resembles *Hoplosaenidea* Laboissière, 1933, but the latter differs in closely spaced frontal tubercles and entire anterior margin of labrum. Having frontal tubercles widely separated by frons and bilobed labrum *Sinoluperus* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963 closely resembles this genus but easily differs in procoxal cavities open posteriorly and bordered anterior margin of the pronotum.

In the description of *Sinoluperoides* Kimoto [1989] incorrectly stated that it differs from *Sinoluperus* in having meso- and metatibiae with spur at apex. Actually, both genera have meso- and metatibiae spined at apex. The difference between these genera is given above in the differential diagnosis.

Sinoluperoides chenchirae sp. n.

(Figs 18–21, 44–46)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1288-1246 m, N 18°56'46", E 99°21'2" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 14.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg. Paratype: 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector as in the holotype, but “h~1105-1099m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024”.

Description. Holotype. Head brown with black labrum, partly darkened frontoclypeus, blurred blackish stroke in middle of frons and blackened areas behind eyes. Pronotum light brown. Elytra brown with basal and apical areas widely blackened, lateral margins and epipleura narrowly blackened. Antennae with antennomere I brown, all other antennomeres darkened. Legs brown with tibiae (except basal part) and tarsi darkened. Ventral side of body brown, metaventrite and apical part of pygidium black. Body length 3.9 mm. General view as in Fig. 18.

Body oblong, very slightly widened posteriorly, about 2.3 times as long as wide. Head (Fig. 19) impunctate, labrum rather large, with deep emargination on apical margin. Labrum surface moderately convex, impunctate, lustrous with several setae along apical margin. Penultimate maxillary palpomere moderately (about 1.5 times wider than previous one) swollen, apical palpomere rather long (just about 1.4 times shorter than previous one), conical. Frontoclypeus trapezoidal, ridged on sides, longitudinally widely concave with two long setae near antennal insertions on each side. Genae very short, about 7.5 times shorter than diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles convex, narrow, strongly transverse and slightly oblique; widely separated to each other with rather deep fossa, delimited behind with thin impressed line, but poorly delimited anteriorly. Surface of frontal tubercles impunctate, smooth, shining. Eyes large, strongly convex, almost round (about as long as wide); interocular space wide (1.67 times as wide as diameter of eye). Vertex covered with microsculpture as well as weak oblique wrinkled behind eyes, with long seta on each side near eye. Antennae filiform, long, 1.27 times as long as body length. Antennomere I large, stout, club-shaped, antennomere II short, almost round. Antennomere III straight, widened at apex. Antennomeres IV–X slightly curved and widened at apex (antennomeres V and X somewhat less curved than rest ones). Antennomere XI almost straight, pointed at apex. Antennomeres I and II glabrous, antennomeres III–X with protruding setae (longer on antennomeres III–VII), last antennomere covered with short semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 15 : 4 : 15 : 22 : 21 : 22 : 22 : 21 : 21 : 20 : 19, width ratio as 6 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Pronotum transverse, 1.5 times as wide as long (widest at anterior half); at level of its posterior angles about 1.5 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight, posterior margin very slightly convex, lateral margins sinuous, slightly notched before anterior and posterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered, lateral and posterior margins bordered. Anterior angles almost rectangular but slightly blunted, very slightly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. All angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta. Several additional short setae placed on lateral margin. Pronotal surface moderately lustrous, covered with sparse, very small punctures; with ovate depression on each side behind middle.

Scutellum triangular, slightly transverse (1.2 times as wide as long); surface lustrous with sparse, small punctures. Elytra 1.64 times as long as wide, very slightly widened at posterior third. Elytral surface with traces of subbasal depression; moderately densely and confusedly covered with distinct small punctures (on apical slope punctuation weakened) with flat interstices. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura moderately wide at anterior quarter, gradually narrowing towards apex. Epipleural surface impunctate and glabrous. Macropterous.

Legs moderately long and slender, covered with pale semi-adpressed setae. All tibiae with spurs. Meso- and metatibiae very slightly curved, apex of metatibiae with rather long (only 1.15 times shorter than metatarsomere I) twisted process: flat and wide for most of length but with narrow hook-shaped apical part, tip pointed (Figs 20, 21). Tarsomere I of all legs not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 10 : 6 : 4 : 11; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 10 : 5 : 4 : 11; of metatarsomeres I–III and V are as 17 : 6 : 5 : 11. Metatarsomere I thin and curved at base then wider and almost straight; longer than length of metatarsomeres I–II combined. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side sparsely covered with pale setae (denser and longer on ventrites of abdomen). Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed with wide rectangular median lobe, surface of which deeply longitudinally depressed. Pygidium convex with widely rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 44–46) 5 times as long as wide, very slightly widened in apical half, with short convergent apical processes

forming acute triangular apex. In lateral view almost straight along underside, triangularly widened in apical third of dorsal side with slightly curved upward tip. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal two-thirds with deep longitudinal lanceolate depression in apical third. Length of aedeagus about 1 mm, width 0.2 mm.

Paratype. Male is similar to the holotype, but slightly lighter: elytra with only basal area (including epipleura) blackened; black colour on pygidium is only at apex as narrow border. Body length 4 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* sp. n. is distinguished from all congeners in the combination of antennae with long setae and modified metatibiae. *Sinoluperoides antennatus* having antennae with long setae is similar to this new species but differs in simple metatibiae. All other members of this genus have antennae without long setae and simple metatibiae.

Etymology. The new species is named after Chenchira Wongphothisan who helped me with various logistical issues during field work in Thailand in 2024.

Vietoluperus alleculoides Medvedev et Dang Dap, 1981

Material. 2♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1246m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 16.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024"; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1246m, N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" - N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 21.V.2024".

Distribution. India (Meghalaya, West Bengal), Laos, Vietnam [Bezdek, 2012], Thailand (new record).

Hyphasis limbatipennis (Jacoby, 1889) (Fig. 22)

Material. 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1226-1400m, N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" - N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 24.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."

Type material is not examined, but the image of the type specimen is available in free access on the website of the Harvard University [Database..., 2025, https://mcbzbase.mcz.harvard.edu/specimen_images/entomology/large/MCZ-ENT00019184_Hyphasis_limbatipennis_had.jpg].

Notes. Among the congeners only some specimens of *H. discipennis* (Jacoby, 1903) from India also have blackish elytra with light margins and are similar to this species, but differ in large body length (5.5 mm); *H. limbatipennis* is 4 mm long. The specimen from Northern Thailand has the body length 4 mm and is fully consistent with the photograph of the type specimen of *H. limbatipennis* (exception of slightly lighter suture). This specimen had typical for *Hyphasis* Harold, 1877 strongly dilated claws of metatarsomeres, which were lost during preparation for photography.

Distribution. India (Assam, Sikkim), Nepal (Katmandu), Myanmar (Bhamo) [Scherer, 1969], Thailand (new record).

Laboissierea minuta Medvedev, 2009 (Fig. 23)

Material. 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1099m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."

Notes. *Laboissierea minuta* was described based on one female from Vietnam [Medvedev, 2009]. My specimen was compared with the holotype of *L. minuta* and they turned out to be identical, except for the shorter body in the specimen from Thailand is 5.7 mm, instead of 6.3 mm in the holotype.

Distribution. Vietnam (Thanh Hóa) [Medvedev, 2009], Thailand (new record).

Podontia lutea (Olivier, 1790)

Material. 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1108m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 12.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1105-1099m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024”.

Distribution. Pakistan, India, China, North Korea, Taiwan, Myanmar, Laos, Northern Vietnam, Malay Peninsula, Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Philippines, New Guinea, Australia [Maulik, 1926; Scherer, 1969; Kimoto, 2000; Medvedev, 2009; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Lee, Yu, 2021], Thailand (new record).

Xuthea orientalis Baly, 1865
(Fig. 24)

Material. 1♀ (PR), “Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov. 100 km N from Chaing Mai, Chiang Dao Hill Resort, 19°33'28.9"N, 99°04'33.3"E, h=494 m, 1. VII. 2017, A. S. Prosvirov leg.”; 2♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 28.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”.

Distribution. India, Nepal, South China, Myanmar, Korea [Maulik, 1926; Scherer, 1969; Kimoto, 2000; Medvedev, 2009; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Bezděk, Konstantinov, 2024], Thailand (new record).

Subfamily Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813

Prionispa cheni Staines, 2007
(Fig. 25)

Material. 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1108m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" - N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 12.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1265m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'44", E 99°22'15" 17.V.2024”; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1099-1040m N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" - N 18°57'8", E 99°20'42" 18.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 25.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same data, but “26.V.2024”.

Notes. This species was described as *Chaeridiona tuberculata* Chen et Yu, 1964 from China (Yunnan), but later transferred to *Prionispa* Chapuis, 1875 and renamed as *Prionispa cheni* Staines, 2007 to eliminate the homonymy [Staines, 2007]. A schematic drawing of its elytra can be found in the original description and the photograph of habitus in the catalogue of Hispinae [Staines, 2015]. *Prionispa cheni* differs from other congeners in uniformly brown antennae and semicircular tubercles on elytra. Until now, this species was known only from Southern China [Staines, 2015; Sekerka, Świętojańska, 2024].

Distribution. China (Yunnan), Northern Thailand (new record).

Prionispa opacipennis Chen et Yu, 1962
(Fig. 26)

Material. 1♂ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28”

21.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♂, 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1226-1400m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" - N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 23.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1310m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" - N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 28.V.2024”.

Notes. A very short diagnosis of *Prionispa opacipennis* and a carefully executed drawing of its habitus are given in the description of this species [Chen et al., 1962]. *Prionispa opacipennis* differs from other congeners in the wider body, brown antennae with four last antennomeres black and in very large, prominent, apically acute tubercles on the elytra.

Distribution. Southern China (Yunnan) [Staines, 2015; Sekerka, Świętojańska, 2024], Northern Thailand (new record).

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